

Epiphanius of Salamis (Cyprus), "Panarion"

also known as "Adversus Haereses, "Against Heresies"

By Lampros Alexopoulos, University of Thessaloniki

Entry tags: Christianity, Early Christianity, Religious Group, Greek, Theology text, Text, Christian Theology, Early Christian Text, Language, Orthodoxy, Byzantine text, Orthodoxy

Epiphanius was born somewhere between 310 and 320. He was perhaps a Romaniote Jew who was born in the small settlement of Besanduk, near Eleutheropolis, in modern-day Israel. He lived as a monk in Egypt, where he was educated and encountered Valentinian groups. In ca. 333 he returned to Palestine where he founded a monastery nearby, which is often mentioned in the polemics of Jerome with Rufinus and John, Bishop of Jerusalem. He was ordained a priest and quickly became the abbot of the monastery he founded, gaining much skill and knowledge. He was able to speak in several tongues, including Hebrew, Syriac, Egyptian, Greek, and Latin. His reputation for learning prompted his nomination and consecration as Bishop of Salamis, in Cyprus, somewhere between 365 and 367, a post which he held until his death. Epiphanius is mostly known for his treatise "Panarion" (from the Latin word "panarium", "breadbasket"), also known as "Adversus Haereses". His treatise operates as a book of antidotes for those bitten by the serpent of heresy. Written between 374 and 377, it forms a sort of handbook for dealing with the arguments of heretics. It lists and refutes eighty heresies, some of which are not to be found in any other surviving documents. Epiphanius begins with the "four mothers" of pre-Christian heresy, i.e. "barbarism", "Scythism" (that is, the Scythian religion, the mythology, ritual practices and beliefs of the Scythian cultures, i.e. ancient Iranic societies who inhabited Central Asia and the Pontic-Caspian steppe in Eastern Europe throughout Classical Antiquity), "Hellenism" (that is, the pagan Greek religion) and "Judaism". He then addresses sixteen pre-Christian heresies that have flowed from them: four philosophical schools (Stoics, Platonists, Pythagoreans, and Epicureans), and twelve Jewish sects. There then follows an interlude, regarding the Incarnation of the Word. Epiphanius subsequently embarks on his account of the sixty Christian heresies, from miscellaneous Gnostics to the various trinitarian heresies of the fourth century, closing with the Collyridians (an Early Christian movement in Arabia whose adherents apparently worshipped the Virgin Mary as a goddess) and the Messalians. Epiphanius's treatise is a valuable source of information on the Christian Church of the fourth century. It is also an important source regarding the early Jewish gospels, such as the Gospel according to the Hebrews circulating among the Ebionites and the Nazarenes, as well as the followers of Cerinthus (an early Gnostic) and the Gospel of Merinthus. A unique feature of the "Panarion" is the way that Epiphanius compares the various heretics to different poisonous beasts, going so far as to describe in detail the animal's characteristics, how it produces its poison, and how to protect oneself from the animal's bite or poison. Origen, for example, is described as "a toad noisy from too much moisture which keeps croaking louder and louder. He compares the Gnostics to a particularly dreaded snake with no fangs. The Ebionites, a Christian sect that followed Jewish law, were described by Epiphanius as a monstrosity with many shapes, who practically formed the snake-like shape of the mythical many-headed Hydra in himself. Epiphanius describes fifty animals, usually one per sect. Furthermore, in the "Panarion" are found some lost works, notably Justin Martyr's work on heresies, the Greek version of Irenaeus's "Against Heresies", and the "Syntagma" written by Hippolytus.

Date Range: 374 CE - 377 CE

Region: Salamis, Cyprus

Region tags: Cyprus

Salamis in Cyprus, the episcopal seat of Epiphanius.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: The Panarion of Epiphanius of Salamis, Book I (Sects 1–46), trans. Frank Williams, Brill, Leiden 1987
- Source 2: he Panarion of Epiphanius of Salamis, Book II and III (Sects 47–80, De Fide) trans. Frank Williams, Brill, Leiden 1993
- Source 3: The Panarion of St. Epiphanius, Bishop of Salamis, trans. Philip R. Amidon, Oxford University Press, 1990
- Source 1: Christian-Friedrich Collatz and Marc Bergermann, "Epiphanius, Band 1 Ancoratus und Panarion haer. 1-33", (Die griechischen christlichen Schriftsteller der ersten Jahrhunderte), De Gruyter 2014
- Source 2: Jürgen Dummer, "Epiphanius, Band 2 Panarion haer. 34-64" (Die griechischen christlichen Schriftsteller der ersten Jahrhunderte), De Gruyter 1980
- Source 3: Jürgen Dummer, "Epiphanius, Band 3 Panarion haer. 65-80. De fide", (Die griechischen christlichen Schriftsteller der ersten Jahrhunderte), De Gruyter 1985

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://ebrary.net/274368/religion/epiphanius_salamis
- Source 1 Description: Epiphanius of Salamis
- Source 2 URL: <https://classicalchristianity.com/category/bysaint/st-epiphanius-of-salamis-ca-315-403/>
- Source 2 Description: Epiphanius of Salamis
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.oca.org/saints/lives/2024/05/12/101356-saint-epiphanius-bishop-of-cyprus>
- Source 1 Description: Saint Epiphanius, Bishop of Cyprus
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.newadvent.org/cathen/13393b.htm>
- Source 2 Description: Epiphanius of Salamis
- Source 3 URL: http://etheses.dur.ac.uk/5089/1/5089_2542.PDF
- Source 3 Description: Orthodoxy and heresy according to saint epiphanius of salamis, Tsiakkas, Christophoros (Durham e-theses)

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: https://web.archive.org/web/20150906041916/http://www.masseiana.org/panarion_bk1.htm
- Source 1 Description: The Panarion of Epiphanius of Salamis A Treatise Against Eighty Sects in Three Books
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.tertullian.org/rpearse/epiphanius.html>
- Source 2 Description: Epiphanius of Salamis: Panarion / Adversus Haereses (Excerpts on the Council of Nicaea)
- Source 3 URL: https://www.tertullian.org/fathers/epiphanius_weights_03_text.htm
- Source 3 Description: Epiphanius of Salamis, Weights and Measures
- Source 1 URL: https://www.documentacatholicaomnia.eu/30_20_0320-0403-_Epiphanius_Salaminis_Episcopus.html
- Source 1 Description: Epiphanius Salaminis Episcopus
- Source 2 URL: https://ia800501.us.archive.org/18/items/EpiphaniusPanarionBksIIIIII/Epiphanius%20-%20_Panarion_%20-%20Bks%20II%20%26%20III%20-%20I.pdf
- Source 2 Description: Epiphanius, Panarion
- Source 3 URL: <http://khazarzar.skeptik.net/books/panariog.htm>
- Source 3 Description: Epiphanius, Panarion (in Greek)
- Source 1 URL: <https://scaife.perseus.org/library/urn:cts:greekLit:tlg2021.tlg002/>
- Source 1 Description: Panarion (Adversus Haereses)

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

- Written

Inked

- with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

- Papyrus

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

- Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Field doesn't know

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Notes: Not exactly. In fact, the "Panarion" can be considered a sequel to the "Anchoratus", another work that Epiphanius wrote in 374, which takes the form of a letter to the church of Syedra in Pamphylia, describing how the "barque" of the church can counteract the contrary winds of heretical thought, and become "anchored". The "Anchoratus" even outlines the content of the Panarion within its text.

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: The "Panarion" lists and refutes eighty heresies, some of which are not to be found in any other surviving documents.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– No

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– Yes

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– No

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– Field doesn't know

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– Field doesn't know

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Epiphanius mentions the Stoic, the Gnostic and the Manichaean belief in reincarnation and the transmigration of souls.

Reference: Alexakis, Alexander . "Was There Life Beyond the Life Beyond? Byzantine Ideas on Reincarnation and Final Restoration". *Dumbarton Oaks Papers* 55 (2001): 155-77.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/1291816>.

↳ In human form?

– No

↳ In animal/plant form?

– Yes

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s)?

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage, etc.)?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma)?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world?

– No

↳ In textual exegesis among practitioners are there debates about reincarnation?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Cremation?

– No

↳ Mummification?

– No

↳ Interment?

– No

↳ Cannibalism?

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying)?

– No

↳ Feeding to animals?

– No

↳ Secondary burial?

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse?

– Yes

↳ Are there specific designations for parts of corpses?

– No

↳ Could parts of corpses become transformed into partial bodily relics?

– Yes

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse?

– Yes

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Field doesn't know

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - No
- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No
- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Yes
- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
 - Yes
- ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Yes
- ↳ Have other knowledge of this world
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings can reward
 - Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Incomprehensible?

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

- No
- ↳ Courage (in battle)
 - No
- ↳ Courage (generic)
 - No
- ↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence
 - Yes
- ↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
 - Yes
- ↳ Generosity/charity
 - Yes
- ↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
 - No
- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
 - Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
 - No
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation

- No
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - No
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - No
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - No
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
 - Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
 - No
- ↳ Optimism/hope
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Field doesn't know

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Field doesn't know

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Field doesn't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– Yes

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– Field doesn't know

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentions the war during the reign of Antiochus Epiphanes, i.e. the revolution of the Maccabees.

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Epiphanius of Salamis (Cyprus), "Panarion", Dechow, Jon . Dogma and Mysticism in Early Christianity : Epiphanius of Cyprus and the Legacy of Origen. Patristic Monograph Series. Leuven: Peeters, 1988.

Reference: Epiphanius of Salamis (Cyprus), "Panarion", Pourkier, Aline . L'hérésiologie Chez Épiphane De Salamine. Christianisme Antique. Paris: Beauchesne, 1992.

Reference: Epiphanius of Salamis (Cyprus), "Panarion", Maraval, Pierr. "Épiphane, "docteur Des Iconoclastes"". In Nicée II, 767-1987 : Douze Siècles D'images Religieuses, 51-62. Paris: Cerf, 1987.

Reference: Epiphanius of Salamis (Cyprus), "Panarion", Solovieva, Olga . "Epiphanius of Salamis and His Invention of Iconoclasm in the Fourth Century A.D.". Fides Et Historia 42, no. 1 (2010): 21-46.

Reference: Epiphanius of Salamis (Cyprus), "Panarion", Young, Richard . Epiphanius of Cyprus: Imagining an Orthodox World. Ann Arbor, Michigan: University of Michigan Press, 2015.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.3998/mpub.7588638>.

Reference: Epiphanius of Salamis (Cyprus), "Panarion", Jacobs, Andrew. Epiphanius of Cyprus: A Cultural Biography of Late Antiquity. Christianity in Late Antiquity. Oakland: University of California Press, 2016.

Reference: Epiphanius of Salamis (Cyprus), "Panarion", Vallée, Gerard. A Study in Anti-gnostic Polemics. Studies in Christianity and Judaism. Ontario: Wilfrid Laurier University Press, 1981.

Reference: Epiphanius of Salamis (Cyprus), "Panarion", Leidwanger, Laurent . "Épiphane De Salamine". In Dictionnaire Des Philosophes Antiques, 184-87. Paris: CNRS Éditions, 2000.

Reference: Epiphanius of Salamis (Cyprus), "Panarion", Χατζηουρανίου, Ιωάννης-Γρηγόριος . Επιφανίου Κύπρου «πανάριον»: Έρευνα Επί Των Πηγών Του Έργου. Thessaloniki: Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.12681/eadd/39626>.

Reference: Epiphanius of Salamis (Cyprus), "Panarion", Lekova, Tatiana . "The Old Church Slavonic Version of Epiphanius of Salamis' Panarion in the Ephraim Kormchaya (the 12TH Century)". Studia Ceranea 9 (2019): 39-57. <https://doi.org/10.18778/2084-140X.09.03>.

Reference: Epiphanius of Salamis (Cyprus), "Panarion", Lennartz, Klaus , and Javier Martinez. Tenue Est Mendacium: Rethinking Fakes and Authorship in Classical, Late Antique & Early Christian Works. Groningen: Barkhuis, 2021.

Reference: Epiphanius of Salamis (Cyprus), "Panarion", Mena, Peter Anthony. "Insatiable Appetites: Epiphanius of Salamis and the Making of the Heretical Villain,". In Studia Patristica 67, 257-63. Leuven: Peeters, 2013.

Reference: Epiphanius of Salamis (Cyprus), "Panarion", Berzon, Todd . "Known Knowns and Known Unknowns: Epiphanius of Salamis and the Limits of Heresiology,". Harvard Theological Review 109, no. 1 (2016): 75-101. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0017816015000498>.

Reference: Epiphanius of Salamis (Cyprus), "Panarion", Shoemaker, Stephen . "Epiphanius of Salamis, the Kollyridians, and the Early Dormition Narratives: The Cult of the Virgin in the Fourth Century". Journal of Early Christian Studies 16, no. 3 (2008): 371-401. <https://doi.org/10.1353/earl.0.0185>.

Reference: Epiphanius of Salamis (Cyprus), "Panarion", Jacobs, Andrew . "Epiphanius of Salamis and the Antiquarian's Bible". Journal of Early Christian Studies 21, no. 3 (2013): 437-64.

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Yes, Alexakis, Alexander . "Was There Life Beyond the Life Beyond? Byzantine Ideas on

Reincarnation and Final Restoration". *Dumbarton Oaks Papers* 55 (2001): 155-77.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/1291816>.